

The Usefulness Of The Core Qualities Of A Client-Centered Psychotherapist To African Clients

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Abstract

Knowing that the client-centered Psychotherapy was developed by Carl Rogers in the United States of America in the 1940s and 1950s, and is widely practiced in Europe and America, the usefulness of this form of therapy to the African clients is yet to be documented. Therefore, this is an inquiry into the usefulness of the core qualities of a client-centered psychotherapist for an African client. The three core qualities are: genuineness, unconditional positive regard and empathy. The authors reviewed literature on the core qualities, and based on their long-time psychotherapeutic experience and practice with black African clients, make assertions on the usefulness of the core qualities. The authors assert that the core qualities are very useful to the majority of the black African clients. They spore the clients to be genuine to themselves, unconditionally prizing of themselves, and be disposed to navigate deeper into sensitive areas of their life experiences, for insight into the source or true cause of their distress, therefore leading to independent decision-making about the best life course for them to chat. The practice of client-centered psychotherapy is therefore recommended for black African clients.

Key words: *Core Qualities, Client-Centered Psychotherapy, Usefulness to African Clients.*

Introduction

The client-centered therapy was formulated by Carl R. Rogers in 1940 based on a phenomenological view of human nature which emphasizes that healthy personality development represents basic congruence between the phenomenal field of experience and the conceptual structure of the self -the realization of this represents freedom for the individual from both internal and external strain as well as an individualized and well-

adjusted value system (Rogers, 1951). The major thesis of the therapy is that a genuine therapist who creates a climate of unconditional positive regard and empathy will inspire psychotherapeutic change in a client if these attitudes are perceived.

The three core qualities or conditions provided by the therapist in a client centered therapy include congruence or genuineness, unconditional positive regard and empathic understanding of the client's internal frame

of reference. For Rogers (1957) these three core qualities function holistically as a gestalt. Also, these qualities are not techniques that the therapist must use and drop at will but they are attitudes which must be learnt, a discipline which has to be imbibed and communicated in the therapeutic situation. When these three core attitudes are communicated by the therapist and perceived by the client, they engender change in the personality structure of the client leading him/her to become a fully functioning person.

Congruence or Genuineness

This can be viewed as “a state of internal wholeness and integration between the therapist’s on-going experiencing and the symbolizing of that experiencing in awareness” (Raskin, Rogers & Witty, 2008). It implies being spontaneous and real, expressing ones feelings and thoughts in an honest and transparent manner. Congruent therapists are those who express the behaviors, feelings or attitudes that the client stimulates in them (Trull & Phares, 2001). Rogers explained it succinctly as follows; “to me being congruent means that I am aware of and willing to represent the feelings I have at the moment, it is being real and authentic in the moment” (Baldwin, 1987, p.51). Genuineness lies at the core of the client centered approach because it conceptualizes the human being as ‘a person’ (Schmid, 2003: p. 108). According to Schmid (2004a), being a person is essentially the ‘process of authenticity, developing ones potential in a constructive way’ (p. 38). Authenticity from person centered perspective is the same as genuineness, a positive sense of self that brings the best out of a person. It is simply the process of maintaining an equilibrium in the process of self-realization and at the same time coexisting with other people in

the world, and meeting up the challenges of keeping relationships in ‘interdependence and solidarity’ (Schmid, 2004: p. 38).

The usefulness of genuineness or congruence bothers around the belief that clients will respond favorably to the authenticity or originality of the therapist which will propel them towards realizing their own genuineness or authenticity. The client perceives the therapist as a real person dedicated to his/her welfare (Trull & Phares, 2001: p. 354). The above authors indicate that this perception is most reassuring and can trigger a sense of personal worth and a desire in the client to unleash his/her inner potential.

Again, genuineness is necessary for the communication and consequent perception of the other two core qualities. According to Watson (1984) if the client perceives the therapist as not genuine then he will not perceive the therapist as communicating the other two conditions (p.19). Thus, genuineness propels an individual towards self -actualization, helping him/her to move towards psychological adjustment. This is expressed in the 15th of 19 assumptions of Rogers’ theory of personality as follows: “psychological adjustment exists when the concept of the self is such that all the sensory and visceral experiences of the organism are, or may be, assimilated on a symbolic level into a consistent relationship with the concept of self” (Rogers, 1951: 481-533). Evidence exist that genuineness is a very crucial factor for therapeutic change (Schnellbacher & Leijssen, 2009) and the most relevant predictor of patient rated therapeutic alliance (Jung, WiesJahn, Rief & Lincoln, 2015).

Unconditional Positive Regard

Unconditional positive regard refers to a warm appreciation or prizing of the other

person and it denotes the therapist's acceptance of 'the clients' thoughts, feelings, wishes, intentions, theories and attributions about causality as unique, human and appropriate to the present experience (Raskin, Rogers & Witty, 2008: p.144). The regard the therapist has for the client should not be colored by anything within or outside the therapeutic situation, be it the characteristics, choices or disclosures of the client. It can be aptly described as respect for the client as a human being. The therapist is expected to exhibit total unconditional positive regard. It involves communicating acceptance, warmth and non-possessive caring of the client as a human being. In the words of Rogers "it involves the therapist's willingness for the client to be whatever immediate feeling is going on- confusion, resentment, fear, anger, courage, love or pride...when the therapist prizes the client in a total rather than a conditional way, forward movement is likely" (Rogers, 1986a: p.198).

The major utility of this core quality is that it helps a client's self-concept to be consistent with his/her life experiences. In other words she acquires a self-concept that is congruent and is able to express an inner subjective reality that has been denied of importance as a result of conditions of worth erected by either parents, peers, spouse or society (Raskin, Rogers & Witty, 2008). It also creates an atmosphere in which the client is free to give up debilitating defenses and can, in the absence of threat, begin to grow as a person (Trull & Phares, 2001). This point is consistent with the seventeenth assumption of Rogers' person centered theory (Rogers, 1951: 533) that 'under certain conditions, involving primarily complete absence of any threat to the self-structure, experiences that are inconsistent with it may be perceived and examined, and

the structure of self revised to assimilate and include such experiences'. Rogers (1951) opined that a person progresses toward respect for others, openness and self-discovery when a trusting and respectful environment is created.

Empathic understanding

Empathic understanding or empathy entails the ability or attitude of understanding the client from her own internal frame of reference; it concerns being in the shoes of the client all through the therapeutic relationship. It means understanding, clarifying and reflecting the feelings held by the client at the moment and in the words of Rogers (1946) as the client explores step by step into the dangerous areas which has been denied to experience.

In empathy, the therapist "tries to get within and live the attitudes expressed instead of observing them, to catch every nuance of their changing nature in a word, to absorb himself completely in the attitude of the other" (Raskin, 2005: p.6-7). It involves an attitude of profound interest in the client's world of feelings, meanings, beliefs, values and feelings (Trull & Phares, 2001).

Empathy can be conceptualized as a cyclic process comprising of three phases (Vanaerschot & Lietaer 2007; Vanaerschot, 1993). It refers to a way of interacting that originates in the therapist's empathic resonance process (phase 1). The therapist tunes into the inner phenomenological world of the client. To achieve this, she uses her own internal world of personal meanings as referents so as to trigger in herself feelings and meanings that tally with the feelings and meanings the client is experiencing. This search for grasping the client's phenomenological world is then communicated through several empathic responses to the client (Phase 2). Phase 3 concerns the effects of the empathic

relationship. Vanaerschot, (1993) believes that these effects are two-fold. The first concerns the effect of empathy as a primary relationship factor through which dedication, acceptance, warmth, and genuine commitment is communicated to the client. This primary therapeutic impact of empathy implies that the other core conditions of congruence and unconditional positive regard are already present. Vanaerschot and Lietaer (2007 p.339) argues that this empathic climate unleashes numerous micro processes which they portrayed as follows:

First, the client feels welcomed and valued as a person, gradually starts to experience herself as worthwhile, and learns to care for herself.

Second, she feels confirmed in her existence as an autonomous person with her own identity; she feels confirmed in her right to exist as an individual within own inner psychic life.

Third, the client learns to accept her own feelings in a nonjudgmental way, thus facilitating self-acceptance.

Fourth, having an empathic listener dissolves alienation.

Finally, the client learns to use her inner experiencing as a trustworthy guide for making choices in life.

Another set of micro-processes are related to empathy as a task relevant variable (Rice, 1983). They consist of two groups with the first involving deepening and facilitating of experiencing (getting more abreast with; feeling more clearly and sharply what one wants to say; coming into contact with new dimensions “at the edge’

of experiencing) and cognitive restructuring (enhancing better information processing by concentrating the client’s attention on aspects of information the client is not attending to; expediting recall of needed information; reflecting in a manner that better organizes the information, thus enhancing further differentiation and integration of meaning) (Vanaerschot & Lietaer, 2007).

In praxis, empathy entails remaining at the emotional level with the client and not deviating from it; exploring the emotional content of the client’s expressions and non-verbal behaviors. One value of empathic understanding is that it generates a deeper appreciation for the client, resulting in non-possessive caring. More importantly, empathy alongside the other two qualities helps the client to understand her feelings, gain insight into the sources of her problems and make decision about the best life course to chat. According to Madu (2018) there are two types of empathy- primary and advanced. While primary empathy is utilized in understanding the feelings and in progressing with the client along emotional lines, advanced empathy is used in making hypothesis about the likely causes or sources of the problem. It is the role of the client to accept or refute them. Advanced empathy as the name implies comes to use after many sessions presumably towards the end of the therapy. Following Rogers’ (1951) theory, empathy helps the individual to perceive himself appropriately (i.e. his sensory and visceral experiences) and also become more understanding and accepting of others as separate individuals (p.533).

According to Vanaerschot and Lietaer (2007), psychotherapists of different persuasions and also within the client centered tradition emphasize various impacts of empathy. One, it facilitates a deep and continuous psychological contact,

whereby a genuine, confirming, and validating encounter of different persons who are conscious of one another's uniqueness can take place. Secondly, from a psychoanalytic perspective, empathy is viewed as a sustained inquiry and immersion of oneself in the experience of the other, resulting in sensitive interpretations that help clients access unconscious experiences. Finally, from an experiential viewpoint, empathy is conceived as an exploration-promoting process in which the therapist resonates with the client's experience, grasping the implicit aspects of it and helping the client to create new meaning.

Generally, Rogerian core conditions have been found to play important roles in therapeutic alliance in various therapies. This is evidenced in meta-analytic studies especially as it concerns empathy and genuineness as integral parts of the therapeutic relationship (Nienhuis, Owen, Valentine, Black, Halford, Parazak, Budge & Hilsenroth, 2018) and in individual studies involving psychotics (Shattock, Berry, Degman & Edge, 2018). It has also been noticed that they play important roles in reducing overall maladjustment and depressive vulnerability (Zuroff, Kelly, Leybman, Blatt, & Wampold, 2010). According to Brooks and Cochran (2016), the core conditions help to build psychological contact, motivates the client to open up to self-reflection, self-realization and self-acceptance.

In a nutshell, the three core qualities contribute to psychological adjustment which is the same as congruence between sensory and visceral experiences and self-concept (Raskin, Rogers & Witty, 2008). They also make an individual to become fully functioning and this is made possible when the person relies on the organismic valuing process which is defined as a

continuous process in which people freely depend on the evidence of their own senses for making value judgments.

The usefulness of the core qualities to African clients:

In order to fully understand the usefulness of the core qualities of a Client-Centred Psychotherapist to African clients, it is important to first of all understand the types of clients that have been reported by some psychotherapists working with African clients in Africa.

Types of African psychotherapy clients:

According to Ebigbo and Ihezue (1981), there are three types of clients (in Africa) - the **traditional, the mixed, and the western oriented types**. The **traditional type** grew up and spent most of his or her formative years in rural areas. Some of them move to the townships at a later stage in their lives. Their world image is analogical, magical and pictorial. They always go to traditional healers when they have health problems (including emotional problems).

The **intermediate mixed type** was either born and bred in the rural areas but moved to a city to work and live as an adult or grew up in a city but continued to have a very strong tie to the rural areas and their customs. This type is a compendium of two cultural systems (the traditional and the western-oriented), because he or she has the tendency of making use of the two methods of healing (traditional and western) at the same time (concurrently). Some of them also consult the religious faith healers. It is worth noting here that the majority (about 80%) of the black African population today would fall (within either the traditional or) the mixed types (Madu, 2013, 2015, 2016; Peltzer, 1991; Pennymon, 2004). African well-trained psychotherapists would be

particularly relevant to this group of clients (especially the mixed type).

Most of the **western-oriented type of clients** were born and bred in the townships. They are educated, mostly Christians or Muslims, they come from monogamous families and their parents are also educated. From childhood, they have always been treated in hospitals and have never thought of going to a traditional healer for treatment. The western forms of psychotherapy would appeal to this group of clients.

Usefulness of Genuineness

Based on many years of experience working with African clients, we observed that many of them who belong to the mixed type are not genuine and realistic to themselves. They left their traditional setting and went to the cities in search of greener pastures, without being properly prepared and equipped for such a move. There in the cities, many of them are frustrated on seeing that their ideas and dreams were rather euphoric. They find out that their present life conditions are often worse than the one they left. Many then realize that 'grass is often greener on the other side of the fence'. To go back to the village would be seen by them as shameful, and to remain in the city without the desired significant improvement in standard of life is rather frustrating. The situation of one finding him/herself on a cross-road leads many to maladjustment and eventually to psychopathology.

However, during client-centered psychotherapy sessions, the attitude of genuineness of the therapist will model and motivate the client to be genuine, authentic, realistic and honest to him/herself. This new attitude will make the client to be able to make healthy decisions that will lead to proper adjustment, balanced personality and eventual self-actualization.

Usefulness of Unconditional Positive Regard

As stated above, many of African clients belong to the Mixed typed of clients. In the cities where they migrated to, many of them do not experience unconditional positive regard. Since they did not meet their often desired goals (of being rich quickly, affluent and/or powerful) they cannot fit into the society of the few rich people. They are often disregarded, looked down upon, and given conditions of worth by the society both in the village and in the city.

The attitude of unconditional positive regard emanating from the therapist therefore helps the client's self-concept to be consistent with his/her life experiences. He/she acquires a self-concept that is congruent and is able to express an inner subjective reality that has been denied of importance as a result of conditions of worth erected by the society (Raskin, Rogers & Witty, 2008). It also creates an atmosphere in which the client is free to give up debilitating defenses and can, in the absence of threat, begin to grow as a person (Trull & Phares, 2001). The client then progresses toward respect for others, openness and self-discovery where a trusting and respectful environment is present (Rogers, 1951).

Usefulness of Empathy:

As earlier stated, empathy entails the ability or attitude of the therapist to understand the client from his/her own internal frame of reference. The therapist steps into the shoes of the client all through the therapeutic relationship; that is, he/she understands, clarifies and reflects the feelings held by the client at the moment, as the client explores step by step the dangerous areas which he/she has been denied to experience (Rogers, 1946).

For an African client who is often of the mixed type, one value of empathic

understanding is that it generates a deeper appreciation for the client, resulting in non-possessive caring. Empathy, alongside the other two qualities, helps the client to understand his/her feelings, gain insight into the sources of his/her problems and make decision about the best life course for him/her to chat. It facilitates a deep and continuous psychological contact, whereby a genuine, confirming, and validating encounter of different persons who are conscious of one another's uniqueness can take place. Empathy will spore sustained inquiry and immersion of the therapist in the experience of the African client, resulting in sensitive interpretations that help clients access unconscious experiences. It will lead to an exploration-promoting process in which the therapist resonates with the client's experience, grasping the implicit aspects of it and helping the client to create new meaning in his/her new situation.

Conclusion

Genuineness, unconditional positive regard, and empathy are very useful to African clients who are maladjusted and psychologically unbalanced. During client-centered psychotherapy sessions, the attitude of genuineness of the therapist will model and motivate the client to be genuine, authentic, realistic and honest to him/herself. This new attitude will make the client to be able to make healthy decisions that will lead to proper adjustment, balanced personality and eventual self-actualization.

For the African client who is often disregarded, looked down upon, and given conditions of worth by the society both in the village and in the city, the attitude of unconditional positive regard emanating from the therapist therefore helps the client's self-concept to be consistent with his/her life experiences. It helps him/her to acquire a self-concept that is congruent and

he/she is able to express an inner subjective reality that has been denied of importance as a result of conditions of worth erected by the society. It also creates an atmosphere in which the client is free to give up debilitating defenses and he/she can, in the absence of threat, begin to grow as a person. The client then progresses toward respect for others, openness and self-discovery where a trusting and respectful environment is present

Empathic understanding generates a deeper appreciation for the African client, resulting in non-possessive caring. It helps the client to understand his/her feelings, gain insight into the sources of his/her problems and make decision about the best life course for him/her to chat. Empathy spores sustained inquiry and immersion of the therapist in the experience of the African client, resulting in sensitive interpretations that help clients access their unconscious experiences. It leads to an exploration-promoting process in which the therapist resonates with the client's experience, grasping the implicit aspects of it and helps the client to create new meaning in his/her new situation. The practice of client-centred psychotherapy is therefore recommended for black African clients.

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